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Exploring the Impact of Mentoring on Teacher Effectiveness in Superdiverse Educational Environments

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Abstract: This research study seeks to examine primary education teachers' perceptions about the contribution of mentoring practice to the effective management of interculturality in the contemporary educational environment. The qualitative methodological approach was followed, whereas semi-structured interviews, as a research tool, were used to explore the theme holistically. The convenience sampling technique was chosen, whereas the sample consisted of ten primary school teachers working in schools in the Region of Western Greece. All participants acknowledge the importance of the role of the mentor in modern school units, provided that he/she has the appropriate mindset and skillset.

Keywords: mentoring, interculturalism, teachers, effectiveness, skills, knowledge, attitudes.

Introduction

The term mentoring is associated with the Homeric epic "Odyssey", as Mentor was a trusted friend of Odysseus who undertook to guide and protect his son, Telemachus, during his absence in the Trojan War. As a concept, in the educational community, it emerged in the early 1980s with the aim of guiding and introducing a newcomer or even a novice teacher to a school unit by a more experienced one, enhancing their self-confidence as well as their personal and professional growth (Giovanangeli et al., 2017). Therefore, as a practice it serves a dual purpose, counselling and psychosocial, whilst the

role of mentor can be undertaken by an experienced colleague, a supervisor or a counsellor (Parker et al., 2021). At the national level, the Ministry of Education introduced the institution of the “mentor” with Law 3848/2010, thus laying the foundations for the professional development of teachers and the upgrading of the quality of education. However, this law was not implemented, despite its importance. The institution of the Pedagogical Advisor-Mentor was finally established by Law 4823/2021 and was implemented in the school year 2022-2023. Article 2 of Government Gazette 4509/2022 lists the duties and responsibilities of mentors, which include, among other things, the identification of teaching and instructional needs, the guidance of teachers in their teaching work and effective communication with students' parents. Mentors are appointed at the beginning of the school year by the principal of the school unit on the basis of their teaching experience, formal qualifications (degrees, postgraduate qualifications, foreign languages, etc.), and previous tenure.

However, considering the significant migrant and refugee inflows in most Western societies, the emerging issue of a mentor who is suitable to support teachers in interculturalism arises (Adebayo & Sunderman, 2023). A review of the relevant literature demonstrates significant benefits from the implementation of intercultural mentoring, such as increased cultural understanding, less sense of superiority, cooperation, inclusive environments, development of skills such as cultural, intercultural and global competence, professional effectiveness and productivity (Swartz et al., 2020; Young et al., 2018).

Research Aim and Research Questions

Considering that the main objective is to understand and deepen our knowledge on a social phenomenon and analyze participants' perspectives on their everyday social domain (school) (Haenssger, 2019), this study seeks to examine primary education teachers' perceptions about the contribution of mentoring practice to the effective management of interculturalism in the contemporary school environment. Specifically, the participants were invited to respond to the following research questions: a) Does the institution of mentoring influence teachers' effectiveness in dealing with interculturality issues? If so, in what ways? If not, why? b) What knowledge, skills and attitudes should a teacher who assumes the role of a mentor in intercultural issues be equipped with?

The qualitative methodological approach was followed, whereas semi-structured interviews, as a research tool, were used to explore the theme holistically (Hennink et al., 2020). Regarding the questions of the interview protocol, they were divided in two parts. The first part covered the demographic and professional information of the participants (age, sex, level of education, years of school experience and experience with migrant students), whereas the second part consisted of four open-ended questions. Finally, all interviews took place in person, and each of them lasted approximately twenty minutes. Finally, the present study endorsed a case-centered thematic analysis of individual answers to questions focusing on the content, whereas the steps followed from the researcher were: (a) familiarizing with the data by collecting the questionnaires and reading the answers that occurred more than once; b) codifying the answers; (c) structuring and organizing the several codes into meanings; (d) reviewing the meanings and finding out which of them is the most common; (e) defining and naming the meanings (Braun & Clark, 2006).

The convenience sampling technique was chosen, and the sample consisted of ten primary school teachers working in schools in the Region of Western Greece. The majority were female, the age of the participants ranged from 25-38 years old, most of them held a postgraduate degree, their work experience was between 3-12 years and all of them had to a certain extent some experience with students with a migrant/refugee background.

Research Results

To start with, all participants acknowledge the importance of the role of the mentor in modern school units, which are characterized by strong diversity, primarily due to the presence of students with immigrant and refugee backgrounds. The mentor can enhance teachers' self-confidence and thus their effectiveness, as they can help them organize teaching, design lesson plans, manage the behaviour of native and non-native pupils, resolve conflict situations, develop interpersonal relationships with parents, facilitate communication with the wider community, familiarize themselves with teaching techniques appropriate for an inclusive classroom and explore the anecdotes of the teachers' own experiences. In particular:

P1: "Mentors could have a significant impact, provided that they are properly trained and qualified. They could help me with how to identify the particular needs of students from another country, how to approach them more effectively so that they open up and feel accepted in the classroom."

P2: "The biggest contribution of mentors for me would be to have help in searching and finding appropriate teaching materials. My school does not have special resources and technical infrastructure... I often have to search for materials on my own from various sources, especially from the internet, but I am not sure about their quality."

P8: "Of course, guidance is valuable especially for the novice teacher who faces many challenges in multilingual classrooms. Communication with both children and their parents is poor as they do not know the Greek language. The mentor can also act as a mediator with the wider community of children."

P10: "In the classroom conflicts often erupt which I find difficult to manage. Children often behave unfairly and harshly towards each other. The weaker a child is, the more racism and bullying he/she receives from the others... Let's not talk about the stereotypes and prejudices towards students who have different nationality, language and religion. In managing these challenges, the role of the mentor would be particularly valuable."

In an attempt to outline the profile of the ideal mentor, the participants were also asked to focus on the appropriate mindset and skillset they should possess. Specifically, they stated that mentors at a first level should know quite a bit about the students' migration background, their countries of origin, elements of their culture, the reasons why they were forced to leave their home country, their migration path, the legal framework and immigration policies of the host country. At a second level, their knowledge should cover the field of pedagogy and inclusive education. In other words, they

need specialized knowledge of right teaching approaches and plans, methods of assessing pupils according to their needs and practices to create an inclusive school environment. In particular:

P.3 "A properly qualified mentor should be knowledgeable about the language, culture and religion of our students from another country. This will help us to better understand their particular needs and to respond to them successfully."

R.4 "I need a mentor who will support me in practice. That is, how to plan appropriate lesson plans, how to implement differentiated instruction, and how to assess children without hurting them."

P5. "In various seminars I have attended, I have heard about translanguaging and the use of technology in teaching students who are migrants or refugees. In practice, however, I find it difficult to implement these practices. So, a trained mentor would support us daily in our efforts to work with these children."

P6. "I would say that it is important for him/her to speak foreign languages and not just the English language that pretty much all colleagues know. He/she needs to be familiar with less "popular" languages in our country, such as Ukrainian, Albanian, Hindi, Dari, so that we can communicate more effectively not only with children but also with their parents."

P9. "Children especially with a migrant background suffer a lot of psychological traumas, they are isolated and marginalized and unfortunately I often feel that I cannot meet their psychological needs. So, ideally for me, the mentor should have important expertise in the field of psychology and trauma management."

In terms of skills and attitudes, participants' responses focused on digital skills, communication skills, interpersonal skills, conflict management skills, teamwork, emotion and trauma management. In addition, the intercultural mentor should be inspiring, cooperative, patient, a good listener, flexible, tolerant, understanding, empathetic, respectful of colleagues, but also appreciated and trusted by his/her colleagues. The interviews with the participating teachers are excerpted below:

P1. "A mentor should have principles and values, such as respecting students, colleagues, parents and the school administration. It is important that he/she can make a substantial and practical contribution to the better functioning of the school, solve problems, be willing to help a colleague who is struggling..."

P4. "Active listening, empathy, respect and willingness to help I would say. And definitely not racist... and be able to manage stereotypical attitudes in school and prejudice from both students and parents."

P7. "I would feel confident with a mentor who is accepted by my school unit, who knows the culture of our school and its unique features."

P8. "As we are all demanding an inclusive school, I would say that an ideal mentor should have high level digital skills to train us ... for example how to use translation tools, chatGPT etc..."

Conclusions

In today's over-differentiated school environments, there is a need for a mentor with specialized knowledge and skills to support and empower teachers on intercultural issues. According to the findings of this research, intercultural mentors should have knowledge focused on students' migrant backgrounds, countries of origin, language, religion and culture, legal frameworks, exploring students' needs, teaching approaches, assessment methods and teaching practices. Empowerment in the process of selecting and designing tools, strategies and methods, developing a sense of community and recording teachers' teaching experiences are also important indicators of an effective mentoring programme (Tenreiro et al., 2020). Mentors and mentees in intercultural relationships should adopt active learning, effective communication, and reflective practices, such as constructive feedback, utilizing a rich repertoire of teaching strategies, direct instruction, group teaching, guided discovery, individualized feedback, translanguaging, simplification or differentiation of the curriculum and discussions, in an effort to increase understanding, acceptance and dismantling of cultural stereotypes (Badia & Clarke, 2021; Glover et al., 2024; Karanikola & Nikolopoulou, 2024; Lash et al., 2022; Spyridonos et al., 2024). In terms of skills and attitudes, participants' responses focused on digital skills, communication skills, interpersonal skills, conflict management skills, teamwork, managing emotions and trauma, and communication with parents. In part we might argue that the intercultural mentor has some of the characteristics of the intercultural mediator, since mediators should also be familiarized with multi-cultural perspectives as well in order to manage ambiguities, and foster a workable environment for all the members of the school community (Bachtsiavanou et al., 2023; Karanikola & Panagiotopoulos, 2025; Theodosiou & Aspioti 2015). Finally, other scholars have also highlighted the importance of interpersonal skills, open-mindedness, and trusting relationships with mentees (Vacarro & Camba-Kelsay, 2018; Wong et al, 2022), sense of duty and responsibility, loyalty, adaptability, tactfulness, discretion, modesty, good manners, sense of tact, impartiality, and reciprocity (UNHCR, 2017; Vještica & Sjekloća, 2020).

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